

Improved compound response prediction with scalable 3D human iPSC-derived cardiac microtissues

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Abstract

The sensitivity and accuracy of human-induced pluripotent stem cell-derived cardiomyocytes (hiPSC-CMs) as disease models would be improved by generating models that more closely resemble the adult heart. Various 3D cardiac models have been developed that bridge the limitations of conventional 2D models but can be highly variable in their responses and require high cell numbers along with complex equipment. As a result, this restricts their suitability for use in high throughput screenings.

We have shown that a tri-cellular combination of hiPSC-derived cardiomyocytes, endothelial cells, and fibroblasts in 3D cardiac microtissues (MTs) enhances cardiomyocyte maturation. Furthermore, the method is inexpensive and requires low numbers of cells per MT. We are now establishing strategies for scalable production and evaluation of MTs. To test the predictivity of MTs compared to conventional 2D monolayers, we performed a blind screen of 12 reference drugs with each having a specific mechanism of action that affects contractility. Some challenging drugs such as PDE3 inhibitors were wrongly classified using 2D models while correctly identified in 3D MTs. Overall, the blind screen in MTs resulted in 92% of drugs being accurately classified, thus showing improved predictivity of drug responses compared to 2D models.

The procedures are also amenable to automation. Using robotics, a 384 well plate of MTs can be formed in <2 minutes, and show similar morphology and functionality as manually seeded MTs. Consequently, 3D cardiac MTs hold great potential for cardiac disease modeling and high throughput screenings